

Memorandum of Understanding between DOAJ and Crossref

Crossref and DOAJ share the aim to encourage the dissemination and use of scholarly research using online technologies and to work with and through regional and international networks, partners, and user communities for the achievement of their aims to build local institutional capacity and sustainability.

This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between DOAJ and Crossref describes this relationship's general terms and conditions.

1. Areas of Collaboration

Crossref and DOAJ will actively engage and collaborate via the following activities:

1.1 Coordinate DOAJ and Crossref support efforts across different support teams

Coordination of this support effort will be undertaken between:

- Crossref Support Centre: support@crossref.org
- DOAJ Support: helpdesk@doaj.org
- Crossref Community Forum: <https://community.crossref.org/>
- The joint “crossref-doaj” Slack channel (private).

1.2 Enhanced support for the least-resourced journals

Both parties will collaborate to support the least-resourced journals. This may include scholar-led or Diamond OA journals and focus on journals from specific regions or marginalised communities. Examples of support might include:

- Assigning DOIs and depositing metadata with Crossref
- Finding ways to improve their DOAJ application experience to help them become indexed
- Collect and ingest their Crossref metadata into DOAJ

- Help them to get preserved via JASPER or similar initiatives
- Help identify other local partners, such as Crossref Sponsoring Organisations, to support their use of Crossref services

Both parties will benefit from collaboration in this area and sharing knowledge.

1.3 Collaborate on data analysis to discover gaps in their data

DOAJ will share its journal CSV with Crossref so that Crossref can cross-match with its data. This will reveal the number of journals indexed in DOAJ that do not have DOIs. Crossref will cover the resources or fees of any data analysis work. Data would be made open under a CC BY license.

A Crossref-DOAJ working group would analyse the results and identify a strategy to help journals get DOIs for their content, investigate barriers to participating in Crossref or DOAJ, gap-fill DOAJ metadata using Crossref's API, or provide specific metadata fields to build out the DOAJ metadata.

1.4 Promotion and Strategic Coordination

Where relevant, we will

- amplify each other's initiatives and blog posts via social media, newsletters, and other channels
- seek opportunities to collaborate on events and speaking opportunities
- participate in relevant committees in each other's organisations (resource permitting), e.g. community and project-based working groups, such as POSI.

Both parties actively participate in the POSI Posse, the working group responsible for ensuring that POSI remains up-to-date and relevant. Both parties will continue to collaborate, sharing knowledge and experience as required. Promoting POSI is done by the POSI Posse, but DOAJ and Crossref are committed to sharing updates about their progress through POSI on their blogs.

The PLACE initiative is another example of strategic coordination to promote each other's work and guidance (alongside other partners). Other working groups or promotional projects may become relevant, such as membership or fee reviews,

research integrity, preservation initiatives, or co-running events or webinars, to be assessed when needed.

1.5 Support development of Crossref features and functionality in DOAJ software and vice versa

Any development priorities and assignments will be mutually agreed upon, recognising the resource limitations of both parties. Any code co-developed by DOAJ and Crossref and incorporated into the DOAJ software, Crossref infrastructure, or elsewhere will be released under the MIT License and the Apache license Version 2. Any translated documentation will also be available on the DOAJ and Crossref sites (as appropriate) under the appropriate Creative Commons CC-BY license.

1.6 Seek to identify further areas of joint action

To address the needs of our respective networks, partners, and user communities, leading to strengthened local and regional capacities. This may include event coordination or sponsorship, new strategic initiatives, joint Ambassador program activities, or seeking additional third-party involvement.

2. Terms of MOU

This MOU is a living document and guideline to help the two organisations collaborate effectively. It is a collaboration in good faith and is not meant as a legally binding contract. We will make this document publicly available for our communities to see the intentions of our collaboration.

The primary DOAJ liaison(s) will be DOAJ's Operations Manager. The primary Crossref liaison(s) will be Crossref's Director of Member & Community Outreach. DOAJ and Crossref liaisons will co-organize meeting times as needed.

3. Termination or adjustments to the MOU

As both parties enter this collaboration in good faith, no official notice is needed to end the collaboration. However, in the interest of best practice, written notice is recommended to allow any current work to end, communication channels to be shut down, and other products of this MOU to be tidied away.

This MOU contains the parties' entire understanding and should only be amended in writing by both parties. Both parties review the document annually, but suggestions for new additions and edits can be made as and when needed and agreed upon by both parties.

4. Signatures

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the undersigned, being duly authorised, have signed the present Memorandum of Understanding:

Crossref

Name: Ginny Hendricks
Title: Director of Member & Community
Outreach
Date: 03-Feb-2024

DOAJ

Name: Joanna Ball
Title: Managing Director
Date: 03-Feb-2024